

A Coup d'oeil Of The Average Blood Glucose and SGPT Levels of Drug Induced Diabetic Experimental Rats Treated with the Cissampelos Pareira L. (Menispermaceae) Root Extract

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Abstract –We discuss a three dimensional model to predict the SGPT levels of the drug induced diabetic rats belonging to the group G4T (group 4 Test) category in the experiments of Ankit Kumar et al. (see, Ankit Kumar, Ravindra Semwal, Ashutosh Chauhan, Ruchi Badoni Semwal, Subhash Chandra, Debabrata Sircar, Partha Roy and Deepak Kumar Semwal, Evaluation of antidiabetic effect of Cissampelos pareira L. (Menispermaceae) root extract in streptozotocin–nicotinamide–induced diabetic rats via targeting SGLT2 inhibition, *Phytomedicine Plus* 2 (2022) 100374, 11pp., <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phyplu.2022.100374>). As per the experimental procedure of Ankit Kumar et al. (op. cit.), the rats of the group G4T were orally administered the Cissampelos pareira root extract at the rate of 500mg/kg/day for twenty eight days after the induction of diabetes in them using streptozotocin and nicotinamide. Treating the SGPT levels of the rats of the group G4T as a function of the number of days of the experimental study and their weekly measured average blood glucose levels, our model explains about 95.71% of the variance in the values of the SGPT of these rats based on the residual sum of squares approach. From the applications point of view, we also present our detailed analysis of the correlation matrix of the dataset under examination.

Keywords: Diabetes, Cissampelos pareira, blood glucose, regression, SGPT, correlation matrix, eigenvalues, eigenvectors.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification 62J02, 62J05, 62J10, 62J99, 62P05, 62P20, 91B62, 91B74, 91B99, 91G70, 91G99.

1. INTRODUCTION

Towards the search of an effective herbal remedy for the treatment of diabetes mellitus, scientists are conducting a number of studies on animals. Among the many medicinal plants which have been used since antiquity by the mankind for the treatment of this ailment and its accompanying symptoms, the climber Cissampelos pareira L. [1] belonging to the Menispermaceae family also holds a great promise in this direction, therefore, many workers have studied the different aspects of this and other plants to investigate in detail their medicinal properties, the mechanism of the therapeutic action of the phytomolecules present in these plants. Some typical works pertaining to this are [2–11]. As diabetes mellitus remains an incurable disorder till date, the effects of this disease in those people who are suffering from it are many [12–14]. The long term complications of diabetes in humans include diabetic nephropathy (which leads to chronic kidney disease), diabetic neuropathy leading to neuropathic pain, vision loss and autonomic dysfunction [13]. To understand and minimize these complications of diabetes,

researchers in the field of medicine and life sciences often study the effect of diabetes and the drugs used to manage this ailment on other related organs of the body like liver, kidneys, etc.

Working on these already well defined lines of research related to the search and development of alternative remedies for the treatment of diabetes mellitus, the work of Ankit Kumar et al. [15] also focused on the effect of the apozem, which was the aqueous-ethanolic extract of the roots of *Cissampelos pareira* L., on the liver and kidneys of the experimental rats. In this work and some of our forthcoming papers on this topic we set our lance on the average blood glucose levels and the SGPT (Serum Glutamic Pyruvic Transaminase) levels of the diabetic experimental rats which were classified under the group 4 test (G4T) of these experiments. We are interested in examining in what manner, if any, the SGPT levels of the rats of this group depended on the number of days of this experiment and the weekly recorded average blood glucose levels of these animals after diabetes was induced in them by injecting them with streptozotocin-nicotinamide and to counter the effects of this disease they were administered with the extract of *Cissampelos pareira* L. for a period of four weeks beginning from day zero (basal day). By examining a number of rival mathematical models for this purpose, using the techniques of regression analysis [16–24], our efforts culminated into the development of some competing three dimensional surface models, which emerged as the best models based on our experience, which successfully explain the pattern of the observed values of the SGPT levels of the rats of the group G4T of the work of Ankit Kumar et al. [15] as functions of the number of days of the experiment and their measured average blood glucose levels. We aim to discuss these models one by one in our upcoming papers. This paper discusses the first model proposed by us in this direction as part of our already ongoing studies [25–28].

The structure of the paper consists of the following. The secondary data for this work is narrated in the second section of the paper. The core model developed by us is thoroughly discussed in the third section with its complete details. In section four we give many mathematical features of the correlation matrix of the model developed in section three. The conclusions in section five finish the paper.

1.1 Abbreviations Used in the Paper

For the sake of convenience, we use the following abbreviations at different places in our work. Some of these abbreviations, like SGPT, are also used in medical terminology and for the sake of conformity we have also used the very same abbreviations as are used by the authors of [15].

G4T: group 4 Test

Day: Day of Experiment

SGPT: Serum Glutamic Pyruvic Transaminase

$1.2345E-03 = 1.2345 \times 10^{-3}$

BG: Blood Glucose

G4BGm: Mean of the blood glucose levels of the G4T rats

$1.2345E+03 = 1.2345 \times 10^3$

G4SGPT: SGPT levels of the group G4T rats

2. DATA FOR THE STUDY

We reproduce below in Table 1 the secondary data for our study, which we have gratefully taken from Table 3 and Table 4 of the work of Ankit Kumar et al. (see, [15, Table 3 and Table 4, p. 6]). We place on record our sincere thanks to the learned authors of [15] and the Publisher of the Journal [15] which is the original source of the data given in Table 1 below.

Template sample paragraph. Define abbreviations and acronyms the first time they are used in the text, even after they have been defined in the abstract. Abbreviations such as IEEE, SI, MKS, CGS, sc, dc, and rms do not have to be defined. Do not use abbreviations in the title or heads unless they are unavoidable.

Table -1: Measurements of the average blood glucose levels in mg/dL and the SGPT levels in (U/L) of the experimental rats showing the effect of the Cissampelos Pareira Root Extract on it.

S. No.	Day	G4BGm (mg/dL)	G4SGPT (U/L)
1.	0	303.9	36.25
2.	7	288.54	37.17
3.	14	250.24	37.98
4.	21	225.35	38.64
5.	28	198.56	60.39

Source: A. Kumar et al. [15]

3. A SURFACE FIT TO MEASUREMENTS OF BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVELS AND SGPT LEVELS OF THE RATS OF THE GROUP G4T

In this section we discuss in detail the three dimensional model formulated by us to explain the variation in the values of the G4SGPT levels of the diabetic rats as reproduced in Table 1 above by assuming that it depends on the values of the day and the corresponding measured average values of the blood glucose levels of these experimental animals. Our detailed studies of a number of possible mathematical models led us to conclude that one of the interesting models which can explain with a great accuracy the trend of the values of G4SGPT in Table 1 with the corresponding values of the Day and G4BGm is the following equation:

$$y = a + bx_1 + \frac{c}{x_2} + \frac{d}{x_2^2} \quad (3.1)$$

where, y represents the response variable G4SGPT (in U/L), the predictor x_1 represents the variable Day and the predictor x_2 represents the variable G4BGm (in mg/dL). We point out that the response y and the predictors x_1 and x_2 of (3.1) are respectively mentioned as 'y', 'x₁' and 'x₂' in the tables and graphs below.

From Table 2 we note certain important points about the model of (3.1). The first thing to be noted is that the coefficient of multiple determination for the model is 0.9570706653, which shows that about 95.71% of variation in the values of G4SGPT (response) is explained by the model with the change in values of the predictors- Day and G4BGm. Further, since the adjusted coefficient of multiple determination is 0.8282826614, as there are four parameters in this model, therefore, according to this criterion only 82.83% of the variability of G4SGPT can be explained by the model, since the adjusted coefficient of multiple determination is always smaller than the coefficient of multiple determination. The value of the Durbin-Watson statistic is 3.12407408002259. We also observe that the highest P-Values of the t - statistic for the four regression parameters, a, b, c, d is 0.77884, which corresponds to the parameter b . This shows that

there are about 77.88% chances that the actual value of the parameter b may be zero, which guides us to the fact that we can remove the parameter b from our model without disturbing much the accuracy of our proposed regression model of (3.1). A number of our numerical experiments conducted so far by us on this issue have definitely shown us that this is indeed true. But we have decided at present to restrain ourselves from moving into that direction, and we propose to expound on this issue in our coming manuscripts. Yet, since there are only two predictors Day (x_1) and G4BGm (x_2), we do not remove this parameter from our model of (3.1) at present, because removing the parameter b from our model of (3.1) at present means that the equation (3.1) reduces to the case of a single variable x_2 , thus we would study the variation of the response $y = G4SGPT$ with only a single predictor $x_2 = G4BGm$, which we have actually done and the results of these studies are earmarked for our future communications on this subject.

Besides showing the values of the four regression parameters a, b, c, d of (3.1) with their respective standard errors, Table 2 also displays the 68%, 90%, 95% and the 99% confidence intervals of these parameters. The lowermost portion of the table shows the Variance Analysis of the model (3.1), with a P-Value of 0.26191, showing that there is a 73.81% chance that at least one of the four regression parameters of (3.1) actually has a nonzero value, which leads us to infer that our model of (3.1) is reliable. It is also observed from Table 2 that the numerical magnitude of the t - statistic is the greatest for the parameter d at 2.05, this underscores the fact that the parameter d is the most significant parameter of the model (3.1).

Table -2: Details of the Model of (3.1) for the dataset of Table 1.

Model Definition: $Y = a+b*x_1+c/x_2+d/x_2^2$
Number of observations = 5
Number of missing observations = 0
Solver type: Nonlinear
Nonlinear iteration limit = 250
Diverging nonlinear iteration limit =10
Number of nonlinear iterations performed = 4
Residual tolerance = 0.000000001
Sum of Residuals = 3.00630631500098E-11
Average Residual = 6.01261263000197E-12
Residual Sum of Squares (Absolute) = 18.11602983058

Residual Sum of Squares (Relative) = 18.11602983058
Standard Error of the Estimate = 4.25629296813318
Coefficient of Multiple Determination (R^2) = 0.9570706653
Proportion of Variance Explained = 95.70706653%
Adjusted coefficient of multiple determination (R_a^2) = 0.8282826614
Durbin–Watson statistic = 3.12407408002259
Regression Variable Results
VariableValue Standard Error t-ratio Prob(t)
<i>a</i> 309.613245242293204.55882574672 1.513565812 0.37169
<i>b</i> 0.6101736693415081.68516498370101 0.3620854191 0.77884
<i>c</i> -139058.22919107789004.3364950211 -1.562375887 0.36246
<i>d</i> 17078569.61191578329445.35498787 2.050384976 0.28888
68% Confidence Intervals
VariableValue 68% (+/-) Lower Limit Upper Limit
<i>a</i> 309.613245242293372.092504033284-62.4792587909907681.705749275578
<i>b</i> 0.6101736693415083.06531510535214-2.455141436010633.67548877469364
<i>c</i> -139058.229191077161898.888084443-300957.11727552122840.6588933662
<i>d</i> 17078569.611915715151261.10072291927308.5111927332229830.7126386
90% Confidence Intervals
VariableValue 90% (+/-) Lower Limit Upper Limit
<i>a</i> 309.6132452422931291.54351399964-981.9302687573491601.15675924194
<i>b</i> 0.61017366934150810.6397946740914-10.029621004749911.2499683434329

<i>c</i> -139058.229191077561955.579762264-701013.808953341422897.350571187				
<i>d</i> 17078569.611915752590452.0823224-35511882.470406769669021.694238				
95% Confidence Intervals				
Variable	Value	95% (+/-)	Lower Limit Upper Limit	
<i>a</i>	309.613245242293	2599.16535170298	-2289.55210646068 2908.77859694527	
<i>b</i>	0.61017366934150	21.4120433159018	-20.8018696465603 22.0222169852433	
<i>c</i>	-139058.229191077	1130906.90037304	-1269965.12956411 991848.67118196	
<i>d</i>	17078569.6119157	105835598.569547	-88757028.9576312 122914168.181462	
99% Confidence Intervals				
Variable	Value	99% (+/-)	Lower Limit Upper Limit	
<i>a</i>	309.613245242293	13021.7034499718	-12712.0902047296 13331.3166952141	
<i>b</i>	0.61017366934150	8107.273389949947	-106.663216280606 107.883563619289	
<i>c</i>	-139058.229191077	5665793.55043181	-5804851.77962288 5526735.32124073	
<i>d</i>	17078569.6119157	530231667.68514	-513153098.073224 547310237.297056	
Variance Analysis				
Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Square F Ratio Prob(F)	
Regression	3	403.880490169421	34.6268300564737	4.313650020.26191
Error	118	11602983058	11602983058	
Total		4421.99652		

Table 3 depicts the computations made from the model of (3.1) for the values of the sample of Table 1, from where see that the residuals vary from a minimum of -3.0175733 U/L to a maximum of 2.790554016 U/L and the largest percentage error is 7.81% for the G4SGPT value of 38.64 U/L, which is quite

manageable. Table 4 below gives some brief descriptive statistics of the sample of Table 1, which we have included here only to give the reader a glimpse of the salient features of the dataset being studied by us. From the correlation matrix of the sample of Table 1 included in Table 4, it is evident that the response G4SGPT is strongly positively correlated ($r = 0.766$) with the predictor Day, as we can see from Table 1 that G4SGPT increases with increase in Day. On the contrary, the response SGPT is strongly negatively correlated ($r = -0.761$) with the predictor G4BGm, as G4SGPT levels increase with decreasing levels of G4BGm. The two predictors Day and G4BGm are most strongly negatively correlated with each other

($r = -0.994$), which is also very much clear from Table 1, where the G4BGm levels of the rats of the Test Group 4 of the authors of [15] show a decline with increasing number of the predictor Day. This fact also supports to some extent the experimental finding of Ankit Kumar et al. [15] that the ethanolic extract of the roots of the plant Cissampelos pareira promises an effective herbal remedy for the lowering of the elevated blood glucose levels of the diabetic experimental rats! In section 4 we discuss the various characteristics of this correlation matrix of the model of (3.1) which is displayed in Table 4. The summary report of the whole computational procedure performed by us for this model is shown in Table 5, which shows that the computations successfully converged in four iterations, with the final merit function value (Residual Sum of Squares) as 18.11602983058. In Table 6 we tabulate the results of our evaluations of the response G4SGPT (y) for different values of the predictors Day (x_1) and G4BGm (x_2) based on the model of (3.1) on an approximately daily basis for a period of one month and the partial derivatives of the response with respect to these two predictors and the parameters are also calculated at these points.

Table -3: Evaluation by the Model of (3.1) for the dataset of Table 1.

x1 Value	x2 Value	y Value	Calc y	Residual	% Error	Abs Residual	Min Residual	Max Residual
0	303.9	36.25	36.95698428	-0.7069842771	-1.950301454	0.7069842771	-3.0175733	2.790554016
7	288.54	37.17	37.08186587	0.08813412531	0.2371109102	0.08813412531		
14	250.24	37.98	35.18944598	2.790554016	7.347430269	2.790554016		
21	225.35	38.64	41.6575733	-3.0175733	-7.80945471	3.0175733		
28	198.56	60.39	59.54413056	0.8458694354	1.400677985	0.8458694354		

The plot of the surface generated by the model of (3.1) corresponding to the dataset of Table 1 is shown in Fig. 1, while the Residual Error Plot of this model corresponding to Table 3 is displayed in Fig. 2. Fig. 3 gives the Residual Normal Probability Plot of the model of (3.1) from which we see that the Residual Normal Probability Plot of the model shows that the residuals deviate both above and below the standard reference line, yet we conclude that the residuals of the model are normally distributed. This fact is confirmed from the brief statistics of the Residuals presented in Table 7, where both the standardized skewness and the standardized kurtosis lie well within the range of -2 to +2, which shows that these Residuals of the Model of (3.1) come from a Normal Distribution. We further confirm this fact from Fig. 4 which depicts the Normal Probability of the Residuals of the Model of (3.1) using the mean and sigma method with their 95% confidence limits (the pink colored curves) around the reference line (the blue colored line). The reader may note from this figure that the five Residuals lie very close to the reference line, which signifies the fact that the Residuals are drawn from a normal population. Another authenticity of this fact comes from the displayed high P-Value =0.9799 of the Shapiro – Wilk test performed by us in

this case, which indicates that these residuals come from a normal distribution with a very high probability. A Surface Plot of the dataset of Table 1 is shown by us in Fig. 5.

Table -4: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix of the sample of Table 1.

Variable	Day	G4BGm (mg / dL)	SGPT (U / L)
Number of Points	5	5	5
Missing Points	0	0	0
Maximum Value	28	303.9	60.39
Minimum Value	0	198.56	36.25
Range	28	105.34	24.14
Average	14	253.318	42.086
Standard Deviation	11.06797181	43.55814987	10.27127694
Correlation Matrix			
	Day	G4BGm (mg / dL)	SGPT (U / L)
Day	1	-0.994134261	0.765841066
G4BGm (mg / dL)	-0.994134261	1	-0.760856601
SGPT (U / L)	0.765841066	-0.760856601	1

Table - 5: Summary Report of the procedure performed.

Beginning non-linear solution for model $a+b*x1+c/x2+d/x2^2$
Obtaining initial estimates
Initial estimates successful
Solving with 1 initial condition(s)
Beginning non-linear iterations
Solution converged to residual change less than 0.0000000001%
Final Merit Function = 18.11602983058
Total number of non-linear iterations = 4
Residual Sum of Squares = 18.11602983058
Solution Complete

Table - 6: Evaluations of SGPT levels for different values of the Day and G4BGm from the model of (3.1) for the sample of Table 1.

S. No.	x1= Day	x2= G4B Gm	y= G4SG PT	$\partial y / \partial x_1$	$\partial y / \partial x_2$	$\partial y / \partial a$	$\partial y / \partial b$	$\partial y / \partial c$	$\partial y / \partial d$

		(mg /dL)	(U/L)						
1.	0	305	37.27 581	6.101736 627684E -01	2.909713 386972E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	- 1.8795918 36735E- 06	3.27869 4687198 E-03	1.074983 885186E -05
2.	0.61 224 5	291.7 755	34.00 418	6.101736 704701E -01	2.58322 0957305 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	6.1224384 92293E- 01	3.42729 9000757 E-03	1.174637 844059E -05
3.	1	301.4	36.85 216	6.101736 708048E -01	2.83238 7553396 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	9.999986 574344E- 01	3.317856 269394E -03	1.1008170 22436E- 05
4.	1.22 449	296.1 837	35.54 397	6.101736 704701E -01	2.705513 603689E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.2244876 98459E+0 0	3.37628 7562642 E-03	1.1399317 70565E- 05
5.	2	283. 4	32.79 864	6.101736 667866E -01	2.30739 5887491 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.9999962 40816E+0 0	3.52858 8142538 E-03	1.245093 427966E -05
6.	2.44 898	274.1 429	31.106 95	6.101736 704701E -01	1.924322 679736E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.448975 396917E+ 00	3.64773 9480378 E-03	1.330600 331671E- 05
7.	3	290. 6	35.159 52	6.101736 681260E -01	2.54808 699684 3E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.999994 361224E+ 00	3.441162 696474E -03	1.184160 070360E -05
8.	3.67 346 9	302.7 959	38.88 1	6.101736 719198E- 01	2.863315 573043E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	3.673462 095378E+ 00	3.30256 0832546 E-03	1.090690 805266E -05
9.	4	283. 4	34.01 899	6.101736 687957E -01	2.30739 5887491 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	3.999992 481633E+ 00	3.52858 8142538 E-03	1.245093 427966E -05

10.	4.28 5714	293. 9796	36.82 2	6.101736 699425E -01	2.646188 566626E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	4.285705 944607E+ 00	3.4016011 40240E- 03	1.157089 031728E -05
11.	5	204. 2	41.254 97	6.101736 691975E -01	- 6.76650 6374703 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	4.999990 602041E+ 00	4.897168 852083E -03	2.39822 6276581 E-05
12.	5.51 020 4	285.1 633	35.35 295	6.101736 688930E -01	2.37059 7500477 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	5.5101966 02190E+0 0	3.50676 9207662 E-03	1.229743 027581E -05
13.	6	218.6	34.54 055	6.101736 694654E -01	- 3.598512 747274E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	5.999988 722449E+ 00	4.57457 4014617E -03	2.09267 2741521E -05
14.	6.73 469 4	296.1 837	38.90 615	6.101736 694184E -01	2.705513 603689E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	6.7346813 41524E+0 0	3.37628 7562642 E-03	1.1399317 70565E- 05
15.	7	243. 8	30.83 823	6.101736 691975E -01	- 1.757927 918874E -02	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	6.999986 842857E+ 00	4.101730 433123E -03	1.682419 254601E -05
16.	7.34 693 9	223.4 49	33.82 367	6.101736 701624E -01	- 2.76490 4125076 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	7.3469251 90753E+0 0	4.47530 255044 9E-03	2.00283 3291806 E-05
17.	8	236. 6	31.84 491	6.101736 697488E -01	- 9.48270 7314189E -02	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	7.999984 963265E+ 00	4.22654 8362500 E-03	1.7863711 06055E- 05
18.	8.57 142 9	258.7 143	32.50 488	6.101736 694563E -01	1.050563 471030E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	8.5714174 92294E+0 0	3.86527 485954 7E-03	1.494034 973985E -05

19.	9	254.6	32.3938	6.101736 690189E-01	7.55650 8592288E-02	1.0000000 00000E+00	8.999983 083673E+00	3.927737 154734E-03	1.5427119 15668E-05
20.	9.795918	291.7755	39.60781	6.101736 693522E-01	2.58322 0957305E-01	1.0000000 00000E+00	9.795892 222741E+00	3.42729 9000757E-03	1.174637 844059E-05
21.	10	279.8	36.87389	6.101736 691975E-01	2.169073 130514E-01	1.0000000 00000E+00	9.9999812 04082E+00	3.57398 8132936E-03	1.277339 117436E-05
22.	10.40816	221.2449	36.34098	6.101736 685685E-01	- 3.131378 363837E-01	1.0000000 00000E+00	1.0408140 43691E+01	4.519886 693864E-03	2.04293 7572537E-05
23.	11	272.6	36.03326	6.101736 713483E-01	1.851267 760086E-01	1.0000000 00000E+00	1.0999979 32449E+01	3.66838 8229771E-03	1.345707 220432E-05
24.	11.63265	282.9592	38.57488	6.101736 682160E-01	2.291140 028067E-01	1.0000000 00000E+00	1.16326281 3537E+01	3.53408 5053942E-03	1.248975 716850E-05
25.	12	283.4	38.90038	6.101736 683452E-01	2.30739 5887491E-01	1.0000000 00000E+00	1.1999983 88921E+01	3.52858 8142538E-03	1.245093 427966E-05
26.	12.2449	201.4082	47.6696	6.101736 681810E-01	- 7.52697 5098709E-01	1.0000000 00000E+00	1.2244876 98459E+01	4.96505 0477564E-03	2.465172 624476E-05
27.	13	229.4	35.9005	6.101736 689502E-01	- 1.869761 578406E-01	1.0000000 00000E+00	1.2999975 56531E+01	4.35920 3760102E-03	1.900265 742209E-05

28.	13.4 693 9	221.2 449	38.20 886	6.101736 690134E -01	- 3.131378 363837E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.3469364 68304E+0 1	4.519886 693864E -03	2.04293 7572537 E-05
29.	14	222.2	38.241 28	6.101736 691975E -01	- 2.970108 578943E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.3999973 68571E+01	4.50045 850403 0E-03	2.025412 674649E -05
30.	14.6 938 8	230. 0612	36.813 46	6.101736 691348E -01	- 1.7781775 64280E- 01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.4693852 38150E+01	4.34667 7664879 E-03	1.889360 672236E -05
31.	15	243. 8	35.719 62	6.101736 701319E- 01	- 1.757927 918874E -02	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.4999971 80612E+01	4.101730 433123E -03	1.682419 254601E -05
32.	15.3 061 2	210.2 245	43.92 021	6.101736 691084E -01	- 5.29957 3739041 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.5306099 45053E+0 1	4.75682 843624 5E-03	2.262741 677187E- 05
33.	16	240. 2	36.45 856	6.101736 692979E -01	- 5.45042 920948 4E-02	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.5999969 92653E+0 1	4.163205 160680E -03	1.733227 720991E -05
34.	16.5 306 1224	298. 2653 061	45.45 21017 8	6.101736 691116E- 01	2.75835 2861196E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.65305811 6920E+01	3.352723 023847E -03	1.1240751 67464E- 05
35.	17	272.6	39.69 43	6.101736 689139E -01	1.851267 760086E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.6999977 17638E+01	3.66838 8229771 E-03	1.345707 220432E -05
36.	17.7 551	296.1 837	45.63 051	6.101736 694459E -01	2.705513 603689E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.7755076 16261E+01	3.37628 7562642 E-03	1.1399317 70565E- 05

37.	18	276.2	41.001 29	6.101736 690189E -01	2.017408 725773E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.7999966 16735E+01	3.620571 613307E -03	1.310853 880708E -05
38.	18.3 673 5	216.8 367	42.75 008	6.101736 693816E -01	- 3.92752 2325553 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.8367315 47688E+0 1	4.6117741 12018E- 03	2.126846 046028E -05
39.	19	211.4	45.56 656	6.101736 691129E- 01	- 5.03863 5581963 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.8999964 28776E+0 1	4.730377 859959E -03	2.237647 469799E -05
40.	19.5 918 4	221.2 449	41.94 461	6.101736 695316E -01	- 3.131378 363837E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.95918031 7534E+01	4.519886 693864E -03	2.04293 7572537 E-05
41.	20	279.8	42.97 562	6.101736 698983E -01	2.169073 130514E- 01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	1.9999962 40816E+01	3.57398 8132936 E-03	1.277339 117436E- 05
42.	20.2 040 8	203. 6122	50.93 437	6.101736 701269E -01	- 6.922108 695123E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.020404 202458E+ 01	4.911303 657479E -03	2.412090 361597E -05
43.	21	297.8	48.05 112	6.101736 691975E -01	2.74680 2941088 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.099996 052857E+ 01	3.35796 4672919 E-03	1.127592 674457E -05
44.	21.4 285 7	302.7 959	49.714 69	6.101736 698465E -01	2.863315 573043E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.1428529 72303E+0 1	3.30256 0832546 E-03	1.090690 805266E -05
45.	22	272.6	42.74 517	6.101736 694171E- 01	1.851267 760086E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.1999970 46356E+0 1	3.66838 8229771 E-03	1.345707 220432E -05

46.	22.6 530 6	274.1 429	43.43 495	6.101736 693325E -01	1.924322 679736E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.2653017 42149E+01	3.64773 9480378 E-03	1.330600 331671E- 05
47.	23	265. 4	42.155 42	6.101736 690577E -01	1.470477 976628E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.299995 676939E+ 01	3.76790 2571844 E-03	1.419708 979091E -05
48.	23.2 653 1	203. 6122	52.80 224	6.101736 695416E -01	- 6.922108 695123E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.326524 877900E+ 01	4.911303 657479E -03	2.412090 361597E -05
49.	24	211.4	48.617 43	6.101736 692800E -01	- 5.03863 5581963 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.399995 488980E+ 01	4.730377 859959E -03	2.237647 469799E -05
50.	24.4 898	210.2 245	49.52 384	6.101736 690814E -01	- 5.29957 3739041 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.448975 396917E+ 01	4.75682 843624 5E-03	2.262741 677187E- 05
51.	25	236. 6	42.217 86	6.101736 688760E -01	- 9.48270 7314189E -02	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.499995 301020E+ 01	4.22654 8362500 E-03	1.7863711 06055E- 05
52.	25.7 142 9	258.7 143	42.96 5	6.101736 692100E -01	1.050563 471030E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.5714222 33468E+0 1	3.86527 485954 7E-03	1.494034 973985E -05
53.	26	229. 4	43.83 276	6.101736 690313E -01	- 1.869761 578406E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.599996 509329E+ 01	4.35920 3760102 E-03	1.900265 742209E -05
54.	26.3 265 3	197	59.86 491	6.101736 696744E -01	- 8.84543 9029879 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.632649 465491E+ 01	5.076151 673073E -03	2.576731 580804E -05

55.	27	200.6	57.29036	6.101736 690189E -01	- 7.75754 548648 8E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.699994 925102E+ 01	4.98505 4235271 E-03	2.48507 6572859 E-05
56.	27.5 510 2	214.6 327	49.26 657	6.101736 694764E -01	- 4.359731 399539E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.755096 821533E+ 01	4.659131 062487E -03	2.170750 225743E -05
57.	28	243.8	43.65 187	6.101736 691975E -01	- 1.757927 918874E -02	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.799994 737143E+ 01	4.101730 433123E -03	1.682419 254601E -05
58.	28.1 632 7	201.4 082	57.38 257	6.101736 694338E -01	- 7.52697 509870 9E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.8163217 06455E+0 1	4.96505 0477564 E-03	2.465172 624476E -05
59.	29	218.6	48.57 454	6.101736 689616E -01	- 3.598512 747274E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.899994 549184E+ 01	4.57457 4014617E -03	2.09267 2741521E -05
60.	29.3 877 6	267.5 306	46.37 924	6.101736 695176E -01	1.590355 912703E -01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.9387704 76301E+01	3.737897 196042E -03	1.397187 544818E -05
61.	30	204.2	56.50 931	6.101736 694915E -01	- 6.76650 6374703 E-01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	2.999994 361224E+ 01	4.897168 852083E -03	2.39822 6276581 E-05
62.	30.3 589 743 6	283.6111111	50.151 33737	6.101736 694955E -01	2.3151158 65166E- 01	1.0000000 00000E+0 0	3.0358917 29752E+0 1	3.525961 573638E -03	1.243240 501877E -05

Fig -1: Plot of the surface of the Model of (3.1) for the sample of Table 1.

Fig -2: Residual Error Plot of the Model of (3.1) for the sample of Table 1.

Fig -3: Residual Normal Probability Plot of the Model of (3.1) for the sample of Table 1.

Table – 7: Brief Summary Statistics of the Residuals of the Model of (3.1)

Summary Statistics for Residuals	
Count	5
Average	-1.8E-7
Median	0.0881341
Standard deviation	2.12814
Coeff. of variation	-1.1823E9%
Minimum	-3.01757
Maximum	2.79055
Range	5.80812
Std. Skewness	-0.216818
Std. Kurtosis	0.362728

Fig -4: Normal Probability Plot of the Residuals of the Model of (3.1).

Surface Plot of the dataset of Table 1

Fig -5: A Surface Plot of the dataset of Table 1.

4. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CORRELATION MATRIX OF THE MODEL OF (3.1)

This section deals with some interesting properties of the correlation matrix of the model defined by (3.1) for the sample of Table 1. We have used the various concepts of Linear Algebra and Matrix Theory, with which the mathematicians are mostly aware of and for the sake of our other interested readers we mention some of the handpicked references [29–34] and for the other concepts utilized by us for our exposition of this section they may access the easily available resources.

The correlation matrix of the model of (3.1) displayed in Table 4 above is essentially a symmetric matrix of order three, which we reproduce below in a convenient mathematical form for the purpose of our study in this section.

$$A := \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.994134261 & 0.765841066 \\ -0.994134261 & 1 & -0.760856601 \\ 0.765841066 & -0.760856601 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

It is a real symmetric positive definite matrix with rank three, which obviously has an empty null space and the value of its determinant and the spanning vectors for its row and column spaces are as shown below:

$$\text{Rank}(A) = 3; \text{ RowDimension}(A) = 3; \text{ ColumnDimension}(A) = 3;$$

$$\text{Determinant}(A) = 0.004836350002;$$

$$\text{Determinant}(A, \text{method} = \text{algnum}) = 0.004836349937$$

$$\text{NullSpace}(A) = \{ \}; \text{ RowDimension}(A) = 3 = \text{ColumnDimension}(A)$$

$$\text{RowSpace}(A) = \left[[1. \ 0. \ 0.], [0. \ 1. \ 0.], [0. \ 0. \ 1.] \right] \quad (4.2)$$

$$\text{ColumnSpace}(A) = \left[\begin{bmatrix} 1. \\ 0. \\ 0. \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0. \\ 1. \\ 0. \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0. \\ 0. \\ 1. \end{bmatrix} \right]; \text{ IsDefinite}(A, \text{query} = \text{'positive_definite'}) = \text{true}$$

Invoking the Gram –Schmidt orthogonalization process, we can have an *orthogonal basis* for A as

$$\text{ord} := \left[\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -0.994134261 \\ 0.765841066 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0.004369820099999998 \\ 0.007352883200000005 \\ 0.003838828899999998 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} -0.201889183079787 \\ -0.0105190338788632 \\ 0.249962900348282 \end{bmatrix} \right], \quad (4.3)$$

and the corresponding *orthonormal basis* for A is given by

$$\text{orthnor} := \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0.6231992836 \\ -0.6195437593 \\ 0.4772716037 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0.466097700949604 \\ 0.784279873414241 \\ 0.409460637665358 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} -0.627993265891283 \\ -0.0327203386473544 \\ 0.777530602416366 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \quad (4.4) \text{The characteristic}$$

polynomial of A as a function of a variable λ is given by

$$\text{CharacteristicPolynomial}(A, \lambda) = -0.0048363500 + 0.846281766\lambda - 3\lambda^2 + \lambda^3 \quad (4.5)$$

which on solving for λ yields the following eigenvalues and the corresponding eigenvectors for A

$$\begin{aligned}
 v, e &:= \text{Eigenvectors}(A) \Rightarrow \\
 v &:= \begin{bmatrix} 2.68554591477729 + 0.I \\ 0.00583529437354411 + 0.I \\ 0.308618790849168 + 0.I \end{bmatrix}, \\
 e &:= \begin{bmatrix} -0.595950234052158 + 0.I & 0.710388726476149 + 0.I \\ 0.594947020166279 + 0.I & 0.703756528606398 + 0.I \\ -0.539334183719560 + 0.I & -0.00863746140177329 + 0.I \\ & -0.374421120970457 + 0.I \\ & 0.388284421061595 + 0.I \\ & 0.842047523915420 + 0.I \end{bmatrix}. \tag{4.6}
 \end{aligned}$$

The scheme of (4.6) entails that corresponding to the first eigenvalue $\lambda_1 = 2.68554591477729 + 0.I$ of A in the vector v , the corresponding eigenvector v_1 is given by the first column of the matrix e as

$$v_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.595950234052158 + 0.I \\ 0.594947020166279 + 0.I \\ -0.539334183719560 + 0.I \end{bmatrix}; I = \sqrt{-1}$$

and similarly for the other two remaining eigenvectors v_2, v_3 of the matrix A corresponding to its two eigenvalues λ_2, λ_3 . The inverse of the matrix A is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{MatrixInverse}(A) = \\
 A^{-1} &= \begin{bmatrix} 87.0692232885649 & 85.0722209582725 & -1.95342590127446 \\ 85.0722209582725 & 85.4957699232816 & -0.101779481964882 \\ -1.95342590127446 & -0.101779481964882 & 2.41857418388470 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{4.7}
 \end{aligned}$$

The LU Decomposition of A , which is a positive definite matrix, by Cholesky's method (Cholesky Decomposition) gives the following square lower triangular factor (matrix) L

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{LUDecomposition}(A, \text{method} = \text{'Cholesky'}) \\
 = L &:= \begin{bmatrix} 1. & 0. & 0. \\ -0.994134261000000 & 0.108152998599132 & 0. \\ 0.765841066000000 & 0.00455134113467118 & 0.643013799946673 \end{bmatrix}, \tag{4.8}
 \end{aligned}$$

and since A is a real symmetric matrix also (as we have already remarked earlier in this section), therefore, the other factor U (the square upper triangular factor (matrix)) is simply the transpose of L , i.e., $U = L^T$, such that $A = LU = LL^T$, which we verify further as under

$$\text{LUDecomposition}(A, \text{method} = \text{'Cholesky'}, \text{output} = \text{'U'})$$

$$= U := \begin{bmatrix} 1. & -0.994134261000000 & 0.765841066000000 \\ 0. & 0.108152998599132 & 0.00455134113467118 \\ 0. & 0. & 0.643013799946673 \end{bmatrix}, \tag{4.9}$$

Multiply(L, U)

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1. & -0.994134261000000 & 0.765841066000000 \\ -0.994134261000000 & 1. & -0.760856601000000 \\ 0.765841066000000 & -0.760856601000000 & 1.000000000000000 \end{bmatrix} = A.$$

It is instructive to have a look at the matrix plot of the correlation matrix A of the dataset of Table 1 given by (4.1). Accordingly, we draw the matrix plot of A in Fig. 6 below:

Matrix Plot of the Correlation Matrix of the sample of Table 1

Fig -6: Matrix Plot of the Correlation Matrix of the sample of Table 1.

(4.7) above gives the inverse A^{-1} of the matrix A defined by (4.1). The matrix plot of this matrix A^{-1} is pictured in Fig.7 underneath. The Eigen Plot of the three eigenvectors v_1, v_2, v_3 given by (4.6) of the matrix A is drawn in Fig. 8. Corresponding to the system of linear equations $Ax_1 = v_1$, for the first eigenvector v_1 of the correlation matrix A , the unique solution is given by the vector $x_1 = (-.2303, .2133, -.2006)^T$ as shown in Table 8 along with the solutions for the remaining two similar systems of linear equations. The solutions of these three systems of linear equations $Ax_i = v_i, i = 1, 2, 3$ are shown in the Figs. (9a), 9(b) and 9(c), where a circle is plotted at the solution, since each of these three systems of linear equations have unique solutions in the three dimensional Euclidean space $\mathbb{R}^3(\mathbb{R})$. At first glance the three graphs of Figs. 9(a), 9(b) and 9(c) appear to be identical, but a closer look reveals that the markings on the three axes are different in all of them, which in fact correspond to the unique solutions x_1, x_2, x_3 of these three systems as shown in Table 8. We have also shown in Table 8 that the sum of the eigenvectors v_1, v_2, v_3 of A is the vector $(-.2600, 1.687, .2941)^T$, which is represented by the black colored vector in Fig. 9(d). By the linear transformation (operator) in $\mathbb{R}^3(\mathbb{R})$, which is defined by the equation

$T(\vec{x}) = A\vec{x}$, $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, the unit sphere is transformed into the 3-space which is shown in Fig. 9(e).

Matrix Plot of the Inverse Matrix of the Correlation Matrix of the sample of Table 1

Fig -7: Matrix Plot of the Inverse Matrix of the Correlation Matrix of the sample of Table 1.

The Images of Unit Vectors and Eigenvectors

Fig -8: The Eigen Plot of the Correlation Matrix of the sample of Table 1.

Table - 8: Solutions of the systems of linear equations $Ax_i = v_i, i = 1, 2, 3$ and sum of the eigenvectors $v_i, i = 1, 2, 3$.

The solution is the point $x_1 = (-.2303, .2133, -.2006)^T$ for the system of linear equations $Ax_1 = v_1$.

The solution is the point $x_2 = (121.7, 120.6, -1.480)^T$ for the system of linear equations $Ax_2 = v_2$.

The solution is the point $x_3 = (-1.210, 1.261, 2.728)^T$ for the system of linear equations $Ax_3 = v_3$.

The sum of the three eigenvectors v_1, v_2, v_3 of the matrix A is the vector $(-.2600, 1.687, .2941)^T$.

The Image of the Unit Sphere
In 3-Space

Fig -9(e): The image of the unit sphere under the transformation $T(\vec{x}) = A\vec{x}$, $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3(\mathbb{R})$.

In Tables 9(a), 9(b) and 9(c) below we give the details of the planes including their basis vectors to which the eigenvectors v_1, v_2, v_3 of the correlation matrix A are respectively normal. These three planes are shown respectively in the Figs. 10(a), 10(b) and 10(c). We finish this section by drawing the surface plot of the eigenvectors v_1, v_2, v_3 of the correlation matrix A , which is shown in Fig. 11.

normal vector: $\langle -.5960, .5949, -.5393 \rangle$
 equation of plane: $-.5960*x + .5949*y - .5393*z = 0$.
 point on plane nearest origin: $\langle 0, 0, 0 \rangle$
 basis vectors: $\langle .5949, .7782, .2010 \rangle, \langle -.5393, .2010, .8178 \rangle$

Table - 9(a): Details of the plane to which the eigenvector v_1 of A is normal.

A Plane

Fig -10(a): Plane to which the eigenvector v_1 of A is normal.

normal vector: $\langle .7104, .7038, -.8637e-2 \rangle$
 equation of plane: $.7104*x+.7038*y-.8637e-2*z = 0$.
 point on plane nearest origin: $\langle 0., 0., 0. \rangle$
 basis vectors: $\langle -.7038, .7104, .3554e-2 \rangle$,
 $\langle .8637e-2, .3554e-2, 1.000 \rangle$

Table – 9(b): Details of the plane to which the eigenvector v_2 of A is normal.

Fig -10(b): Plane to which the eigenvector v_2 of A is normal.

normal vector: $\langle -.3744, .3883, .8420 \rangle$
 equation of plane: $-.3744*x+.3883*y+.8420*z = 0$.
 point on plane nearest origin: $\langle 0., 0., 0. \rangle$
 basis vectors: $\langle .3883, .8903, -.2379 \rangle$, $\langle .8420, -.2379, .4841 \rangle$

Table – 9(c): Details of the plane to which the eigenvector v_3 of A is normal.

Fig -10(c): Plane to which the eigenvector v_3 of A is normal.

Surface Plot of the eigenvectors of the Correlation Matrix A .

Fig -11: The surface plot of the eigenvectors of the Correlation Matrix A .

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we successfully fitted a model given by (3.1) above to explain the trend of the measured values of SGPT levels of the experimental diabetic rats belonging to the group G4T in the experiments of Ankit Kumar et al. [15] by treating the observed SGPT levels as functions of the two predictors – Day and G4BGm. Based on sorting the various competing models of our numerical experiments for this purpose by the residual sum of squares statistic, the proposed model can explain about 95.71% variation in the levels of SGPT of the rats and thus it poses itself as a reliable mathematical model for the problem under discussion. We also presented our detailed analysis of the correlation matrix of the dataset of Table 1 in section 4 of the paper using various concepts of Linear Algebra and Matrix Theory. We shall also discuss some other competing models for the dataset of Table 1 of this paper in our forthcoming papers. Besides this we shall also delve into the question of studying the variation of the G4SGPT values with G4BGm after removing the parameter b from the model of (3.1) and its various consequences, as we have remarked above. Before parting we would definitely like to disclose here that our studies conducted so far on the variation of the SGPT values with those of G4BGm in Table 1 after the removal of the parameter b from (3.1) have led us to the formulation of a number of closely contesting two-dimensional models which shall also be the subjects of our future papers on this topic.

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